

TECHNISCHE
UNIVERSITÄT
WIEN

Sentiment Analysis of Enhanced Twitter Data Using Custom Sentiment Scoring

SENTI-TWIT-FAIR

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Lead partner:	
Version:	1.0
Status:	
Dissemination level:	PU: Public
Document link:	

Sentiment Analysis of Enhanced Twitter Data Using Custom Sentiment Scoring has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. .

Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Sentiment Analysis of Enhanced Twitter Data Using Custom Sentiment Scoring project, delivered in [M4]. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the [section name] section.

COPYRIGHT NOTICE

This work by parties of the Sentiment Analysis of Enhanced Twitter Data Using Custom Sentiment Scoring project is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>). The Sentiment Analysis of Enhanced Twitter Data Using Custom Sentiment Scoring project is funded by the European Union Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement No .

DELIVERY SLIP

	Name	Partner/Activity	Date
From:			
Moderated by:			
Reviewed by:			
Approved by:			

DOCUMENT LOG

Issue	Date	Comment	Author
1.0	[dd.mm.yyyy]		

TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values

EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

CONTRIBUTORS

Role	Persons
Project Coordinator Principal Investigator	
Project Coordinator Principal Investigator	Hachem Bouhamidi, e12438592@student.tuwien.ac.at
Contributors	Hachem Bouhamidi, e12438592@student.tuwien.ac.at, Researcher

Content

1. Executive Summary	5
1.1. Introduction	5
1.2. Data Summary	5
1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse	5
1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users:	6
2. FAIR data	6
2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	6
2.2. Making data accessible	7
2.3. Making data interoperable	8
2.4. Increase data re-use	8
3. Other research outputs	9
4. Allocation of resources	9
5. Data security	10
5.1. Storage and backup facilities	10
5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data	10
5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data	11
6. Ethical and legal issues	11
6.1. Personal data	11
6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership	Error! Bookmark not defined.
6.3. Ethical issues	11
7. Other issues	11

1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

[name of data manager] will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Sentiment Prediction Outputs for Twitter Dataset	Structured text	CSV, PNG, TXT, JOBLIB	100 - 1000 MB	no

Description for "Sentiment Prediction Outputs for Twitter Dataset":

Predicted sentiment labels for the test set of tweets, generated by a machine learning model (HistGradientBoostingClassifier) trained on enhanced Twitter data TUWRD DOI : 10.70124/c8v83-0sy11

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Enhanced Twitter Dataset for Sentiment Analysis	TU Wien Research Data Repository (DBRepo) – DOI: https://doi.org/10.82556/9rx-7t26		no

Description for "Enhanced Twitter Dataset for Sentiment Analysis":

An enriched Twitter dataset containing cleaned tweets, custom-calculated sentiment scores, and additional metadata. It was used as the training and testing base for the sentiment prediction model.

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data was reused from an existing dataset titled "Sentiment Analysis of Enhanced Twitter Data with Custom Sentiment Scoring," published in the TU Wien Research Data Repository (DBRepo) with the DOI <https://doi.org/10.82556/9rzx-7t26>. The dataset contains cleaned and sentiment-enhanced tweets. It was reused for training, validating, and testing a machine learning model designed for sentiment classification. The data was processed using Python programming language (version 3.11), leveraging libraries such as pandas for data manipulation, scikit-learn for feature extraction (bag-of-words model) and model training, matplotlib and seaborn for data visualization, and joblib for model serialization. A HistGradientBoostingClassifier was applied to classify the sentiments into predefined categories. All outputs, including trained models, performance reports, and prediction results, were generated using open-source tools and saved in standard formats (.csv, .png, .txt, .joblib).
Reused Data: The input dataset Enhanced Twitter Dataset for Sentiment Analysis was obtained from the DBRepo repository. DOI: [10.82556/9rzx-7r26]
Produced Data: The outputs of the project, including the trained model, feature extractor, model performance report, and confusion matrix, were deposited into TUWRD. DOI: [10.70124/c8v83-0sy11]
The code used for downloading data, preprocessing text, training and evaluating the machine learning model, and saving outputs is available on GitHub at: <https://github.com/Hachembouhamidi/Sentiment-Analysis-Twitter-DaSt2025>. The repository includes the Jupyter notebook, trained model, vectorizer, performance reports, and prediction outputs. It is publicly accessible to ensure reproducibility of the results.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Members of the scientific community

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The data will be structured into clearly named CSV files (e.g., train_data.csv, validation_data.csv, test_data.csv) alongside model files (sentiment_model.joblib, count_vectorizer.joblib), performance reports (model_performance.txt), and visualizations (confusion_matrix.png). Each file will include a version number in its metadata or filename if updated. Data versions will be tracked manually during the project lifecycle to ensure traceability.

Metadata will include the dataset title, description, creator (with ORCID and affiliation), version, license information, creation date, used methods (e.g., machine learning model type), and the original dataset's DOI. Descriptions of each file and column names will also be provided to make the dataset easily findable and reusable. This will help others to identify, discover, and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests. Some datasets cannot be published and even need to be deleted at the end of the project. See section 5 for more details.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2025-04-28	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	CC-BY-4.0

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: The data can be accessed and reused using standard data science libraries such as pandas (Python). For reproducing the machine learning results, Python programming environment and packages such as scikit-learn are required.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided that there are no data protection concerns.

Documentation will consist of README files explaining the project structure, data sources, software dependencies, and steps for reproducing the analysis. Additionally, detailed descriptions of each dataset column, model training parameters, and evaluation methods will be included. Scripts used for training and testing the model will be available to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

The following data quality checks will be done: standardised data capture, data entry validation and peer review of data.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

...

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Coverage of costs:

...

The data manager will direct the data management process overall, with [the work package leaders] being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, backup and other quality control activities are maintained. The researchers will be responsible for routine supervision of the dataset development.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by Coordinator (acting as the person responsible for data management and DMP) in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU Wien's Campus IT. The data will be stored on TU Wien servers.

R1 (Enhanced Twitter Dataset for Sentiment Analysis), P1 (Sentiment Prediction Outputs for Twitter Dataset) will be stored on TUfiles: TUfiles is a central and readily available network drive with daily backups and regular snapshots provided by TU.it. It is suitable for storing data with moderate access requirements, but high availability demands that allows full control of allocating authorisations. Only authorized staff members will have access.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	no access
R1	writing	reading only	no access

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and rights of use

The following individual(s) hold rights and control access to the project data: The dataset "Enhanced Twitter Dataset for Sentiment Analysis" and the dataset "Sentiment Prediction Outputs for Twitter Dataset" will be controlled by the project owner, Hachem Bouhamidi. No external access will be granted during the research phase.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?